

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.1241 Max: 63.2758	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1171 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 640-642	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
DEFINITION cut for bench built wall 1163				Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU: Filled by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1163
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction		FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are				SOIL/MATRIX	
Anthropic		Geological		Organic	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
				clay ____% silt ____% sand ____% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
				Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	
				Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)					
Northern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original	
Southern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			
Western Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		cut by 1152	
Eastern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE					
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):		
Is abutted by:			Abuts:		
Is covered by:			Covers:		
Is cut by: 1152			Cuts: 1165, 1176, 1189		
Is filled by: 1163			Fills:		
OBSERVATIONS Soil around wall previously excavated; cut not visible after excavation of fill - photos taken when wall was partially excavated.					
DESCRIPTION					
Position within sector: South-Central Area B					
Shape: Rectangular					
For layers complete this section:					
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):					
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):					
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):					
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)					
For cuts complete this section:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):		
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight			See sketch on reverse.		
Cut sides: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping					
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular					
How is cut top edge? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded					
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> rounded					
Observations:					

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Cut for a trench built rubble wall SU 1163. The crushed tufo floor in this area seems to have been used as the bottom of the cut. This cut, as well as its wall, was later cut by a grave trench (cut = su 1152, "Fran") at its western limit.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by J. FARR

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PDFd by

on

Entered by

on